

1 **Supplementary information for: “Buzzy bees: Improving the monitoring of**
2 **pollinator activity in sunflower fields with continuous acoustic recording and**
3 **deep learning”**

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32 **Supplementary information A - Setting up the audiomoths**

33 **Firmware version:** 1.4.2

34 **Sample rate:** 16 kHz

35 **Gain:** Low-Medium

36 **Sleep duration:** 5 s

37 **Recording duration:** 900 s

38 **Start recording:** 6 am

39 **End recording:** 10pm

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41 **Table S1** - Overview of records. The percentage of loss is due to a hard drive failure
 42 and sound recorders that fell to the ground

Field	Theoretical number of records of 10s	Number of 10s records we have	Number of hours recorded	Percentage of loss	Fields included in the comparison between acoustic monitoring and honeybeecounts in field transects
12	152 460	147 220	409	3.5	X
116	151 740	125 194	348	17.5	X
376	132 840	131 966	367	0.7	X
1823	151 110	110 758	308	26.7	
2187	131 310	130 279	362	0.8	X
2230	143 190	141 997	394	0.8	X
2939	180 450	179 194	498	0.7	X
3107	207 180	157 846	438	23.8	

3253	148 860	147 657	410	0.8	X
3271	159 840	118 384	329	25.9	X
4566	141 840	140 346	390	1.1	X
5572	171 630	135 085	375	21.3	X
5595	148 680	147 448	410	0.9	X
5867	192 690	191 389	532	0.7	X
6223	169 470	145 255	403	14.3	
7029	139 860	105 708	293	24.4	
7413	156 870	127 159	353	18.9	
7507	162 450	144 321	401	11.2	X
8690	133 380	90 503	251	32.1	

9523	99 450	69 789	194	29.8	X
10106	183 510	92 117	256	49.8	
10486	175 950	105 273	292	40.2	
10626	95 310	86 702	263	9	X
12446	145 620	143 887	400	1.2	X
12473	121 770	69 586	193	42.9	
13138	138 240	114 444	318	17.2	X
13253	159 480	158 204	439	0.8	X
14499	108 360	82 404	229	24	X
15339	106 650	71 567	199	32.9	
17019	126 180	93 872	261	25.6	X

45 **Table S2** - Number of sound events labeled per class of the training dataset A

Sound event class	Number of events labeled
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	198
<i>Bombus sp.</i>	20
Unidentified pollinator	7
Bird	9
Human voice	201
Car	216
Noise (i.e. mechanical noise or experimenter noise)	1077
Wind	124

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48 **Table S3** - Number of recordings sampled in E) Classifier testing

49 For score classes 5 and 6, it was impossible to obtain the theoretical number of
50 records in certain fields due to an insufficient number of detections, which explains
51 why the number of sampled records does not correspond to the theoretical number of
52 records for these classes.

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Confidence score group	Confidence score range	Theoretical number of records per field	Total theoretical number of records per confidence score group	Number of recordings
1	0-0.5	7	210	210
2	>0.5-0.6	9	270	270
3	>0.6-0.7	11	330	330
4	>0.7-0.8	13	390	390
5	>0.8-0.9	17	510	501
6	>0.9	21	630	399

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56 **Table S4** - Number of sound events labeled per class for the training datasets B, C
 57 and D

Sound event class	Number of events labeled	Example of sound event class sonograms (duration of each sonogram is indicated under them)
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	198	5.3s
<i>Bombus sp.</i>	20	8s
Unidentified pollinator	12651	6.3s
Bird	734	6.2s
Turtledove and pigeon	625	5s

Cock	225	6.8s
Corvidae	32	7.9s
Dog	85	8s
Sheep	4	6.9s
Human voice	B: 378 C: 2078 D: 3678	7.2s
Car	1343	5.2s
Motorcycle	562	6.8s

Truck	171	4.6s
Plane	980	7.5s
Bell	50	5.7s
Noise (i.e Mechanical noise or experimenter noise)	4567	4.6s
Wind	1436	5.5s

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60 **Table S5** - Description of each classifier tested

Classifier name	Method used	Training dataset	Batchsize	The best AUC
RF-1	Random forest	B	NA	0.856
RF-2	Random forest	C	NA	0.869
RF-3	Random forest	D	NA	0.878
CNN-1	Convolutional neural networks	B	4	0.953
CNN-2	Convolutional neural networks	B	8	0.939
CNN-3	Convolutional neural networks	B	16	0.949
CNN-4	Convolutional neural networks	B	32	0.931
CNN-5	Convolutional neural networks	C	4	0.955

CNN-6	Convolutional neural networks	C	8	0.952
CNN-7	Convolutional neural networks	C	16	0.942
CNN-8	Convolutional neural networks	C	32	0.939
CNN-9	Convolutional neural networks	D	4	0.955
CNN-10	Convolutional neural networks	D	8	0.956
CNN-11	Convolutional neural networks	D	16	0.957
CNN-12	Convolutional neural networks	D	32	0.938

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63 **Table S6** - The confusion matrix for the best classifier (CNN-11) at the threshold
64 retained for comparative analyses between acoustic monitoring and transect counts.

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Real positive	82	9
Real negative	51	428
	Predicted positive	Predicted negative

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